

A Appendix

A.1 Data

In this section, we outline the Common Crawl data used, detailing the cutoff dates and the data collection period. The dumps span multiple years, with varying distributions of weeks per year (cf. Table 4), which is critical for understanding the temporal coverage of the training data.

Year	Week
2014	42
2015	14, 48
2016	22, 44
2017	13, 47, 51
2018	5, 9, 13, 17, 22, 26, 30, 34, 39, 43, 47, 51
2019	4, 9, 13, 18, 22, 26, 30, 35, 39, 47, 51
2020	5, 10, 16, 24, 29, 34, 40, 45, 50
2021	4, 10, 17, 21, 25, 31, 39, 43, 49
2022	5, 21, 27, 33, 40, 49
2023	6, 14, 23, 40, 50

Table 4: List of dumps by year and week.

The data spans from 2014 to 2023, with earlier years (2014-2016) containing fewer dumps but often representing a larger dataset per dump. The latest available data cutoff is from 2023 (week 50), giving the model a comprehensive span of nearly a decade of web data.

This periodization ensures that the model has exposure to a wide temporal range of web content, with a balanced emphasis on both earlier, higher-density dumps and more recent, frequent dumps, providing a robust training corpus.

A.2 Training Ablation Experiments

We present here the training ablations and our methodology in more detail. Table 5 summarizes the main results, while Figures 7 and 14 display training loss curves of the various ablations against the baseline (“original” in the plots). The loss curves are throughput-normalized where appropriate.

We conducted the experiments on 2.6B scale, and focused on 3 downstream-tasks: (1) ARC Easy [40], (2) HellaSwag [44], and (3) LAMBADA [18]. Because the models often achieved better-than-random performance in these evaluation tasks and because they test different abilities of the model, they were deemed a good-enough proxy measure of general downstream improvements.

Consistent throughput across runs is critical in comparing in the compute-equivalent setting. While guaranteeing consistent throughput across runs was not possible due to external factors (such as nondeterministic job layout on the super-computing cluster, or varied I/O throughput due to a shared parallel file system), we believe the variance to be small enough (up to a percent) not to significantly affect our findings. Due to encountering errors as well as resource constraints, we had to cut several ablations short. Because we believe our findings to be meaningful nonetheless, we include unfinished ablations as well.

We assume that every training iteration takes the average amount of time and thus apply the same proportional normalization to every step. This assumption is fine for the conducted ablations because there is no theoretical throughput variance between steps. We normalize across time with regard to the baseline to compare in the compute-equivalent setting using the following formula:

$$t_i(s) = s \frac{1}{\bar{T}_i},$$
$$s'_i = \text{time-normalize}_i(s) = s \frac{t_i(s)}{t_{\text{baseline}}(s)},$$

where t is a time (e.g., in seconds), i is one of the ablation experiments (including the baseline), s is the iteration (step) to normalize time until, \bar{T} are averaged throughput values (e.g., iterations per second), and s'_i is a time-normalized step for experiment i . This normalization allows us to compare the training and validation loss at each point in time and express that a method with lower loss at the same point in time as the baseline is more compute-efficient up to that point in time with regard to that loss.

The following ablations were conducted:

1. **SwiGLU**: replace the first layer of the MLP part of the Transformer with a T5-style (i.e., without biases) [13, 61] Swish-activated [42] gated linear unit layer [58, 66].
2. **Untied in/out embedding**: learn separate weights for the input embedding and output “unembedding” layers [61].
3. **No Linear biases**: remove all bias terms in Linear layers [61]. The ablation ran until 33 000 steps and was not evaluated due to being deemed too far from completion.
4. **No GPT-like weight init**: whether to scale weight initialization in layers that a residual path leads into as a function of depth [65]. The ablation ran until 39 000 steps and was not evaluated due to being deemed too far from completion.
5. **Head scaling**: multiply each Attention head’s output by a learned scalar factor [49].
6. **No dropout**: disable dropout [38] in all layers [61]. The latest checkpoint available for evaluation was at 21 000 steps. While it showed a strongly monotonic improvement over the baseline, it is especially hard to interpret improvement in training loss in the dropout vs. no dropout setting. We evaluated this change even though it was far from finishing training because its improvements were so drastic.
7. **RMSNorm**: replace LayerNorm normalization layers [30] with root mean square layer normalization layers [12].

8. **NoPE**: no position embedding [5]; completely remove position embeddings.
9. **ALiBi**: replace the Rotary position embedding [27] with the Attention with linear biases position embedding [39]. Because we were unable to use an optimized ALiBi kernel for this ablation, throughput-normalization was not considered out of fairness.
10. **GQA (2 groups)**: replace multi-head Attention with grouped-query Attention [23] with 2 groups (i.e., 2 key/value heads).
11. **Adan (4× base LR)**: replace the AdamW optimizer with the Adan optimizer [57], using the baseline’s learning rate multiplied by 4. The increased learning rate was chosen based on previous small-scale experiments.
12. **2×/4× base LR**: use the baseline’s learning rate multiplied by 2 or 4. The ablation with a factor 4 increase did not run until completion; its checkpoint used for evaluation was saved at 48,000 steps, 5 100 steps before the end of training, and was deemed “close enough” to completion to provide a fair evaluation comparison, especially due to its noticeable training loss improvements.

Change	ARC Easy	HellaSwag	LAMBADA	Interpretation
-	0.535	0.355	0.503	0
SwiGLU	0.527	0.361	0.507	+
Untied in/out embedding	0.524	0.355	0.498	-
No Linear biases (33k st.)	-	-	-	+?
No GPT-like weight init (39k st.)	-	-	-	-
Head scaling	0.527	0.356	0.493	-
No dropout (21k st.)	0.492	0.334	0.414	+?
RMSNorm	0.530	0.358	0.502	0
NoPE	0.516	0.351	0.486	-
ALiBi	0.527	0.349	0.486	-
GQA (2 groups)	0.513	0.346	0.459	?
Adan (4× base LR)	0.544	0.374	0.522	+?
2× learning rate	0.540	0.369	0.514	+
4× learning rate (48k st.)	0.545	0.371	0.517	+

Table 5: Selected evaluation results. Bold is best, underlined is better than baseline. Italic means the run was evaluated before finishing. Ablations without values were not evaluated. The rightmost column contains a subjective interpretation/recommendation, where “+”, “-”, “0” indicate a positive, negative, and neutral interpretation, respectively. “?” indicates it is difficult to make a conclusive statement.

We decided to implement most of the “free lunch” improvements and some neutral results based around current research results at that point in time while disregarding some findings that were deemed too experimental and/or risky.

Notably, we decided to use neither Adan nor 4× the learning rate despite these changes yielding the best results. Instead, to minimize risks, we opted to use the same learning rate as Llama-2 [22]. Due to our inexperience at training at this scale, we were worried about possible convergence problems if we had chosen these important parameters incorrectly.

In summary, the chosen changes are: SwiGLU, no biases, no dropout during pre-training, RMSNorm, GQA (with 2 groups). GQA was chosen despite its comparatively worse results to optimize for inference in the post-training setting.

Hyper-Parameter	Value
Training Objective	CLM
Activation Function	SwiGLU
Seq Length	4096
Position Embeddings	Rotary
Num Layers	32
Hidden Size	4096
FFN Hidden Size	13440
Num Attention Heads	32
Head Dim	128
Group Query Attention	yes
Num Query Groups	2
Normalization	RMSNorm
Learning rate	3e-4
Min learning rate	1.5e-5
Disable bias in linear	yes
Hidden dropout	0.0
Attention dropout	0.0
Optimizer	AdamW
Beta1	0.9
Beta2	0.95
Data-type	bf16

Table 6: Hyper-Parameter Configuration

A.3 Impact of Educational Content

Figures 15-19 demonstrate the development of the model downstream performance between 0.99T and 6T tokens for English, French, German, Finnish, and Estonian. The grey area in the figures highlights the ablation in which we compare the performance of the EU24 data to the FineWeb-EDU dataset between 2.85T and 3T tokens.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-TQA	EU21-MMLU
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.548	.554	.588	.495	.556
Salamandra-7B	.523	.589	.637	.449	.417
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.505	.513	.534	.472	.501
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.464	.470	.511	.448	.426
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-control	.409	.393	.433	.456	.353
Bloom-7B1	.348	.319	.355	.464	.256
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.520	.558	.619	.449	.453

Table 7: Results on multilingual benchmarks for 21 European languages with base models.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-TQA	EU21-MMLU
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.601	.634	.687	.474	.607
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.580	.632	.662	.453	.571
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.568	.630	.702	.424	.514
Pharia-1-LLM-7B	.559	.635	.686	.453	.461
Salamandra-7B	.545	.631	.685	.429	.435
Bloom-7B1	.406	.448	.501	.416	.260
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.541	.608	.674	.405	.478

Table 8: Results on multilingual benchmarks for 6 Languages with base models.

A.4 Evaluation

The Tables 7-10 present the results of our base model compared to related base models.

A.4.1 Toxicity

We evaluate our models compared to other instruction-tuned models on the PolygloToxicityPrompts benchmark [17]. We report results from PTP_{SMALL}. Our evaluation settings are the same as those detailed in Section 3.4 of [17], except the repetition parameter K which is set to $K = 1$ in our setup. We further report toxicity and profanity metrics provided by the Perspective API [6]. For both attributes $i \in \{\text{Profanity, Toxicity}\}$ we report the EMPIRICAL PROBABILITY denoted EP_i as well as the AVERAGE denoted A_i as defined in Section 3.4 of [17]. Tables 32 to 36 show the results by language as well as aggregated, for the languages German, English, French, Italian and Spanish.

Teuken’s low toxicity scores can be attributed to the combination of our extensive filtering process and instruction tuning. First, we removed harmful content using heuristic rules and perplexity scores from KenLM. The resulting model still indicated room for improvement in toxicity. Therefore, for the last part of the training data, consisting of two trillion tokens, we applied an additional machine learning–based filter specifically trained to detect adult content. Combined with subsequent instruction tuning, this significantly reduced Teuken’s overall toxicity.

A.5 Instruction Tuning

In the following, we provide more insights regarding our instruction tuned model. Particularly, we give an overview of the training datasets that we employed for instruction tuning the model (Appendix A.5.2), and present additional evaluation results (Appendix A.5.3).

A.5.1 Training details - Hyperparameters

We display the utilized hyperparameters in Table 37.

A.5.2 Instruction Tuning Datasets

Table 38 and Table 39 provide an overview of the employed instruction tuning datasets and DPO datasets, respectively.

A.5.3 Instruction Tuning Evaluation Results

In Figure 20, we present additional evaluation results of MT-Bench-X [1].

A.6 Software

We selected our training framework based on efficiency in terms of throughput (TFLOP/s) and maintenance. Therefore, we decided to train our models based on a fork of Megatron-LM [55] that supports various scalability features ensuring efficient training of transformer-based decoder-only models. Implementation contributions include a tensor-model-parallel SwiGLU layer [42, 66, 13, 61] and fused RMSNorm [12] integration. In particular, we made use of 3D parallelism, i.e., data, tensor, and pipeline parallelism. Additionally, we used ZeRO [55] to reduce memory requirements further by sharding the optimizer state.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-TQA	EU21-MMLU
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.527	.522	.549	.503	.535
Salamandra-7B	.514	.572	.617	.457	.410
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.475	.466	.482	.479	.473
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.422	.406	.435	.458	.391
Pharia-1-LLM-7B	.349	.296	.332	.457	.310
Bloom-7B1	.325	.267	.296	.483	.254
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.511	.539	.597	.466	.443

Table 9: Results on multilingual benchmarks across 15 exclusive European languages with base models.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-TQA	EU21-MMLU
Salamandra-7B	.536	.612	.664	.447	.423
Bloom-7B1	.376	.376	.419	.452	.258
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.533	.587	.650	.432	.464

Table 10: Base model results on multilingual benchmarks across the 10 common languages (Czech, Dutch, English, French, Greek, Italian, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, and Spanish). The tables include mean accuracy across languages.

A.7 Training Infrastructure

We trained our models for 812.321 GPU hours on a supercomputer, which comprises 936 compute nodes, each containing $4 \times$ NVIDIA A100 (40 GB) GPUs connected via NVLink3 intra-node and through Mellanox HDR200 InfiniBand (IB) inter-node.

We utilized a maximum of 1024 GPUs and a minimum of 32 GPUs for our training runs, achieving perfect to near linear scaling behavior. Ablations were conducted to optimize the training runs for the system and network configuration in terms of parallelization, memory, and GPU utilization. The model employed tensor and pipeline parallelism of 2, along with sequence parallelism and optimizer sharding. State-of-the-art methods, such as flash attention and mixed-precision training, were also enabled, leading to maximum utilization of the hardware.

When scaling beyond 64 GPUs, the training became more susceptible to hardware failures. We encountered issues with high-bandwidth NCCL communications triggering hardware failures initiated by the IB port restarting. To enhance the robustness and fault tolerance of the training runs against node and port failures, we used environment variables for extending timeouts such as `NCCL_IB_TIMEOUT` and `UCX_RC_TIMEOUT`, along with `NCCL_ASYNC_ERROR_HANDLING=1`. Furthermore, model checkpoints were saved at regular intervals and whenever errors or exit signals of the scheduler (Slurm) were detected.

The training runs were actively monitored using TensorBoard and custom cluster monitoring tool aiding to better visualization and debugging opportunities. We also implemented an automatic job submission strategy to combat hardware failures and queue times.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.591	.610	.621	.615	.520
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.584	.620	.609	.540	.568
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.577	.589	.632	.590	.495
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.575	.625	.691	.514	.469
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.567	.618	.669	.482	.498
Aya-23-8B	.564	.589	.645	.519	.501
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.561	.615	.679	.512	.439
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.552	.595	.598	.551	.465
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.546	.616	.659	.450	.457
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.543	.614	.644	.466	.451
Salamandra-7B	.531	.601	.645	.432	.445
Bloomz-7B1	.340	.299	.307	.309	.442
Bloom-7B1	.323	.294	.310	.262	.427
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.588	.607	.689	.477	.577
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.530	.576	.636	.470	.436

Table 11: Task accuracies for the German language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.706	.753	.846	.627	.597
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.692	.736	.802	.690	.541
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.662	.715	.819	.661	.452
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.654	.727	.829	.635	.426
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.624	.698	.797	.551	.449
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.605	.681	.790	.543	.404
Aya-23-8B	.617	.670	.779	.565	.454
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.623	.712	.775	.519	.486
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.607	.702	.770	.503	.454
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.609	.711	.772	.508	.446
Salamandra-7B	.586	.695	.771	.453	.423
Bloomz-7B1	.496	.550	.610	.372	.452
Bloom-7B1	.449	.546	.606	.257	.389
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.635	.685	.820	.516	.517
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.581	.667	.771	.512	.372

Table 12: Task accuracies for the English language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.612	.638	.667	.624	.521
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.606	.647	.660	.549	.567
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.593	.620	.675	.598	.478
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.581	.656	.722	.511	.435
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.575	.643	.698	.477	.482
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.573	.627	.652	.562	.451
Aya-23-8B	.564	.610	.687	.519	.441
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.563	.643	.713	.504	.393
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.555	.635	.681	.461	.444
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.551	.636	.684	.458	.428
Salamandra-7B	.532	.624	.683	.430	.391
Bloomz-7B1	.461	.500	.579	.367	.396
Bloom-7B1	.431	.501	.573	.262	.387
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.592	.634	.710	.476	.550
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.535	.602	.673	.466	.399

Table 13: Task accuracies for the French language.

(a) “SwiGLU” ablation (time-normalized)

(b) “Untied in/out embedding” ablation (time-normalized)

(c) “No Linear biases” ablation (time-normalized)

(d) “No GPT-like weight init” ablation

(e) “Head scaling” ablation (time-normalized)

(f) “No dropout” ablation

Figure 7: Training loss curves using (a) SwiGLU, (b) untied input and output embeddings, (c) no Linear biases, (d) no GPT-like weight initialization, (e) per-head scaling factors, and (f) no dropout. All plotted against the baseline.

Figure 8: “RMSNorm” ablation (time-normalized)

Figure 9: “NoPE” ablation (time-normalized)

Figure 10: “ALiBi” ablation (*not* time-normalized out of fairness)

Figure 11: “GQA (2 groups)” ablation (time-normalized)

Figure 12: “Adan” ablation (time-normalized)

Figure 13: “2x/4x base LR” ablation

Figure 14: Training loss curves using (a) RMSNorm, (b) no position embedding, (c) Attention with linear biases position embedding, (d) grouped-query Attention with 2 groups, (e) the Adan optimizer, and (f) 2x or 4x the base learning rate. All plotted against the baseline.

Figure 15: Downstream performance of the base model from 0.99T to 6T tokens for English. The grey area highlights the ablation comparing the performance of EU24 data to the FineWeb-EDU dataset between 2.85T and 3T tokens. After 4T tokens, we replaced the English FineWeb-EDU and continued training until 6T tokens with DCLM-Baseline.

Figure 16: Downstream performance of the base model from 0.99T to 6T tokens for French. The grey area highlights the ablation comparing the performance of EU24 data to the FineWeb-EDU dataset between 2.85T and 3T tokens. After 4T tokens, we replaced the English FineWeb-EDU and continued training until 6T tokens with DCLM-Baseline.

Figure 17: Downstream performance of the base model from 0.99T to 6T tokens for German. The grey area highlights the ablation comparing the performance of EU24 data to the FineWeb-EDU dataset between 2.85T and 3T tokens. After 4T tokens, we replaced the English FineWeb-EDU and continued training until 6T tokens with DCLM-Baseline.

Figure 18: Downstream performance of the base model from 0.99T to 6T tokens for Finnish. The grey area highlights the ablation comparing the performance of EU24 data to the FineWeb-EDU dataset between 2.85T and 3T tokens. After 4T tokens, we replaced the English FineWeb-EDU and continued training until 6T tokens with DCLM-Baseline.

Figure 19: Downstream performance of the base model from 0.99T to 6T tokens for Estonian. The grey area highlights the ablation study comparing the performance of EU24 data to the FineWeb-EDU dataset between 2.85T and 3T tokens. After 4T tokens, we replaced the English FineWeb-EDU and continued training until 6T tokens with DCLM-Baseline.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.616	.635	.649	.614	.565
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.590	.625	.627	.545	.565
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.589	.647	.708	.519	.483
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.588	.624	.655	.592	.483
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.575	.627	.679	.480	.515
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.575	.629	.702	.517	.451
Aya-23-8B	.565	.596	.663	.513	.488
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.561	.601	.618	.556	.471
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.558	.626	.658	.472	.478
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.554	.616	.670	.457	.473
Salamandra-7B	.536	.610	.656	.432	.448
Bloomz-7B1	.368	.339	.380	.326	.428
Bloom-7B1	.363	.345	.390	.263	.453
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.588	.634	.688	.474	.556
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.529	.590	.646	.475	.404

Table 14: Task accuracies for the Italian language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.618	.641	.673	.627	.530
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.602	.655	.654	.548	.552
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.597	.632	.679	.606	.470
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.591	.656	.729	.520	.458
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.578	.648	.693	.480	.492
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.576	.636	.712	.516	.438
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.574	.628	.651	.561	.456
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.566	.643	.687	.483	.450
Aya-23-8B	.566	.608	.677	.523	.456
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.552	.636	.681	.453	.437
Salamandra-7B	.549	.634	.686	.434	.443
Bloomz-7B1	.478	.517	.582	.379	.434
Bloom-7B1	.437	.509	.573	.260	.407
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.597	.647	.710	.474	.557
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.541	.620	.666	.473	.404

Table 15: Task accuracies for the Spanish language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.608	.625	.651	.622	.535
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.590	.625	.625	.551	.558
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.587	.624	.662	.596	.466
Aya-23-8B	.570	.608	.674	.517	.479
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.563	.611	.661	.471	.508
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.562	.614	.624	.561	.449
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.557	.631	.667	.473	.459
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.542	.603	.649	.448	.468
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.541	.593	.623	.490	.457
Salamandra-7B	.535	.619	.669	.430	.422
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.526	.578	.615	.491	.420
Bloomz-7B1	.455	.490	.555	.373	.403
Bloom-7B1	.433	.490	.553	.255	.434
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.587	.636	.699	.476	.538
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.533	.593	.655	.473	.412

Table 16: Task accuracies for the Portuguese language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.583	.589	.589	.596	.558
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.568	.577	.597	.580	.518
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.563	.584	.550	.519	.597
Aya-23-8B	.559	.578	.638	.505	.516
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.546	.558	.550	.537	.540
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.546	.598	.629	.465	.492
Salamandra-7B	.533	.595	.634	.418	.485
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.490	.516	.499	.433	.510
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.474	.494	.488	.438	.477
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.377	.322	.336	.352	.497
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.372	.314	.333	.350	.490
Bloomz-7B1	.346	.287	.302	.299	.497
Bloom-7B1	.341	.287	.302	.258	.518
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.578	.592	.650	.470	.601
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.525	.558	.607	.457	.479

Table 17: Task accuracies for the Romanian language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.565	.577	.571	.581	.529
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.553	.566	.583	.556	.508
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.550	.580	.545	.510	.563
Aya-23-8B	.536	.569	.611	.499	.467
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.536	.591	.624	.461	.467
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.528	.564	.540	.520	.487
Salamandra-7B	.512	.587	.627	.405	.429
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.466	.484	.485	.435	.463
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.456	.461	.477	.436	.449
Bloomz-7B1	.334	.267	.296	.287	.488
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.332	.275	.307	.302	.444
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.330	.270	.310	.306	.433
Bloom-7B1	.327	.280	.298	.259	.472
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.567	.602	.649	.458	.557
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.518	.562	.609	.450	.453

Table 18: Task accuracies for the Czech language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.576	.571	.605	.596	.533
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.564	.582	.589	.532	.555
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.562	.556	.616	.569	.506
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.541	.601	.663	.462	.436
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.535	.561	.580	.542	.457
Salamandra-7B	.522	.594	.659	.425	.410
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.490	.500	.541	.452	.466
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.472	.484	.529	.448	.429
Aya-23-8B	.441	.404	.476	.440	.444
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.364	.319	.358	.364	.416
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.358	.325	.354	.339	.412
Bloomz-7B1	.330	.268	.306	.306	.440
Bloom-7B1	.322	.270	.306	.253	.461
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.578	.597	.692	.471	.555
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.528	.566	.642	.467	.437

Table 19: Task accuracies for the Danish language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Aya-23-8B	.541	.556	.622	.478	.506
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.537	.574	.633	.425	.514
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.530	.510	.540	.536	.535
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.519	.504	.553	.513	.504
Salamandra-7B	.518	.570	.633	.387	.480
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.379	.309	.376	.362	.470
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.377	.321	.383	.364	.440
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.350	.302	.354	.311	.434
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.350	.289	.354	.315	.440
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.325	.251	.289	.275	.483
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.323	.247	.290	.275	.481
Bloom-7B1	.323	.254	.287	.254	.496
Bloomz-7B1	.322	.243	.285	.273	.488
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.541	.566	.653	.367	.579
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.515	.548	.620	.429	.463

Table 20: Task accuracies for the Greek language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.510	.541	.576	.441	.480
Salamandra-7B	.482	.530	.574	.407	.419
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.472	.443	.452	.501	.492
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.464	.444	.463	.487	.464
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.369	.311	.338	.372	.456
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.364	.293	.342	.389	.431
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.352	.290	.334	.322	.461
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.347	.287	.333	.327	.442
Aya-23-8B	.345	.286	.327	.334	.434
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.318	.257	.295	.288	.434
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.316	.258	.297	.286	.423
Bloomz-7B1	.315	.256	.288	.248	.466
Bloomz-7B1	.311	.263	.285	.271	.425
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.535	.536	.595	.440	.570
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.485	.501	.552	.441	.448

Table 21: Task accuracies for the Estonian language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.505	.491	.511	.527	.491
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.493	.483	.523	.512	.454
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.512	.532	.602	.439	.476
Salamandra-7B	.491	.540	.603	.415	.404
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.410	.359	.404	.416	.463
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.403	.358	.406	.426	.424
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.374	.328	.371	.351	.446
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.367	.317	.368	.354	.431
Aya-23-8B	.356	.299	.348	.349	.428
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.325	.275	.305	.304	.417
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.324	.281	.300	.289	.427
Bloomz-7B1	.307	.267	.296	.269	.395
Bloomz-7B1	.313	.258	.301	.247	.446
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.550	.559	.631	.447	.564
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.493	.520	.590	.446	.415

Table 22: Task accuracies for the Finnish language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.544	.524	.558	.566	.530
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.533	.522	.558	.547	.506
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.526	.553	.592	.444	.514
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.521	.515	.504	.488	.576
Salamandra-7B	.502	.541	.589	.400	.476
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.492	.492	.496	.501	.479
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.434	.424	.422	.398	.491
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.426	.412	.417	.403	.470
Aya-23-8B	.378	.299	.347	.374	.493
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.334	.265	.297	.297	.478
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.333	.265	.294	.292	.478
Bloomz-7B1	.336	.268	.294	.272	.509
Bloomz-7B1	.332	.276	.290	.244	.517
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.548	.546	.614	.447	.585
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.501	.526	.575	.434	.471

Table 23: Task accuracies for the Hungarian language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.527	.554	.589	.444	.519
Salamandra-7B	.503	.557	.580	.394	.481
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.470	.447	.442	.498	.495
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.465	.444	.447	.482	.486
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.370	.292	.337	.365	.485
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.366	.289	.339	.374	.463
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.352	.283	.328	.326	.472
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.349	.277	.326	.327	.466
Aya-23-8B	.396	.318	.378	.390	.499
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.322	.248	.298	.286	.456
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.319	.246	.300	.283	.447
Bloomz-7B1	.318	.254	.291	.267	.459
Bloom-7B1	.322	.261	.293	.259	.476
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.543	.538	.605	.439	.591
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.494	.508	.556	.430	.482

Table 24: Task accuracies for the Lithuanian language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.469	.432	.438	.488	.518
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.468	.432	.443	.482	.515
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.514	.533	.565	.433	.526
Salamandra-7B	.502	.525	.570	.406	.506
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.375	.295	.326	.352	.525
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.373	.292	.329	.368	.502
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.366	.294	.320	.326	.522
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.358	.281	.321	.324	.507
Aya-23-8B	.358	.283	.324	.338	.486
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.334	.267	.294	.294	.480
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.328	.260	.296	.280	.473
Bloomz-7B1	.330	.261	.291	.276	.494
Bloom-7B1	.327	.259	.293	.255	.503
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.537	.520	.585	.425	.619
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.495	.492	.549	.427	.514

Table 25: Task accuracies for the Latvian language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.597	.592	.629	.608	.561
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.582	.595	.593	.534	.608
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.580	.583	.632	.586	.520
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.560	.603	.655	.471	.511
Aya-23-8B	.560	.576	.640	.509	.513
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.557	.595	.652	.470	.510
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.553	.568	.584	.546	.512
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.548	.595	.642	.448	.505
Salamandra-7B	.539	.593	.648	.431	.483
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.512	.530	.563	.468	.485
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.498	.515	.549	.466	.465
Bloomz-7B1	.342	.264	.305	.303	.494
Bloom-7B1	.331	.277	.310	.253	.486
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.584	.599	.685	.472	.582
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.538	.577	.644	.462	.468

Table 26: Task accuracies for the Dutch language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.563	.591	.572	.496	.593
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.547	.554	.544	.546	.546
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.545	.595	.642	.449	.493
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.538	.563	.568	.488	.531
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.534	.540	.559	.516	.520
Salamandra-7B	.519	.586	.638	.389	.463
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.464	.470	.480	.369	.538
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.448	.464	.474	.344	.511
Aya-23-8B	.422	.386	.421	.403	.477
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.335	.264	.305	.270	.500
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.333	.253	.310	.263	.507
Bloomz-7B1	.332	.259	.295	.259	.517
Bloomz-7B1	.326	.260	.292	.251	.500
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.557	.581	.661	.387	.597
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.515	.545	.614	.410	.492

Table 27: Task accuracies for the Bulgarian language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.566	.570	.576	.572	.546
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.556	.579	.561	.506	.577
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.556	.569	.585	.552	.516
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.547	.592	.634	.460	.502
Aya-23-8B	.548	.560	.620	.495	.518
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.536	.568	.553	.519	.506
Salamandra-7B	.525	.595	.632	.409	.464
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.474	.507	.500	.432	.457
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.458	.486	.489	.426	.430
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.336	.282	.314	.313	.436
Bloomz-7B1	.334	.274	.299	.287	.478
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.332	.275	.316	.297	.440
Bloomz-7B1	.326	.272	.297	.260	.476
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.576	.589	.656	.456	.603
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.518	.555	.606	.444	.468

Table 28: Task accuracies for the Polish language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.535	.537	.521	.559	.525
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.530	.581	.613	.462	.465
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.523	.522	.531	.542	.496
Salamandra-7B	.507	.586	.611	.411	.421
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.476	.468	.468	.475	.491
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.458	.454	.464	.484	.432
Aya-23-8B	.456	.429	.489	.450	.454
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.422	.418	.438	.412	.420
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.418	.406	.430	.412	.425
Bloomz-7B1	.330	.262	.291	.281	.488
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.326	.264	.302	.313	.426
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.324	.255	.301	.302	.437
Bloomz-7B1	.316	.263	.294	.255	.453
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.557	.569	.635	.454	.570
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.505	.537	.591	.451	.442

Table 29: Task accuracies for the Slovak language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.513	.510	.489	.539	.513
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.528	.574	.599	.453	.486
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.518	.537	.510	.495	.531
Salamandra-7B	.512	.571	.600	.419	.456
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.502	.509	.501	.525	.474
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.503	.529	.506	.501	.476
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.427	.432	.437	.394	.444
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.420	.418	.434	.393	.437
Aya-23-8B	.391	.334	.379	.395	.457
Bloomz-7B1	.319	.242	.292	.275	.467
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.318	.254	.300	.299	.419
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.317	.259	.300	.295	.413
Bloom-7B1	.313	.256	.294	.246	.454
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.551	.557	.615	.452	.580
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.510	.530	.576	.446	.487

Table 30: Task accuracies for the Slovenian language.

Model	Average	EU21-ARC	EU21-HeSw	EU21-MMLU	EU21-TQA
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.601	.594	.636	.596	.579
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.585	.601	.603	.527	.608
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B	.592	.586	.644	.579	.558
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.566	.620	.664	.459	.519
Salamandra-7B	.543	.608	.660	.428	.477
Mistral-7B-v0.3	.555	.576	.595	.542	.507
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.510	.512	.548	.452	.526
Occiglot-7B-eu5	.490	.496	.531	.445	.486
Aya-23-8B	.459	.418	.482	.444	.494
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr-aligned	.378	.324	.352	.360	.476
Pharia-1-LLM-7B-ctr	.374	.320	.347	.340	.490
Bloomz-7B1	.339	.263	.294	.301	.497
Bloom-7B1	.332	.275	.298	.257	.498
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.579	.586	.677	.463	.591
Teuken-7B-Base (Ours)	.527	.552	.627	.458	.473

Table 31: Task accuracies for the Swedish language.

Model	EP _{Profanity}	A _{Profanity}	EP _{Toxicity}	A _{Toxicity}
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.162	.184	.188	.235
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.186	.188	.214	.236
Aya-23-8B	.212	.216	.235	.262
Bloomz-7B1	.122	.132	.149	.173
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.175	.184	.193	.226
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.205	.207	.221	.251
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.069	.136	.083	.165

Table 32: PTP_{small}^{English} evaluated on instruction-tuned models.

Model	EP _{Profanity}	A _{Profanity}	EP _{Toxicity}	A _{Toxicity}
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.035	.081	.029	.097
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.022	.066	.022	.086
Aya-23-8B	.039	.085	.030	.098
Bloomz-7B1	.017	.049	.020	.066
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.054	.097	.045	.116
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.045	.091	.037	.102
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.010	.077	.009	.079

Table 33: PTP_{small}^{German} evaluated on instruction-tuned models.

Model	EP _{Profanity}	A _{Profanity}	EP _{Toxicity}	A _{Toxicity}
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.264	.258	.250	.268
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.156	.171	.138	.179
Aya-23-8B	.227	.232	.221	.245
Bloomz-7B1	.127	.129	.119	.136
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.301	.281	.275	.272
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.314	.294	.286	.288
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.140	.195	.122	.185

Table 34: PTP_{small}^{French} evaluated on instruction-tuned models.

Model	EP _{Profanity}	A _{Profanity}	EP _{Toxicity}	A _{Toxicity}
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.153	.188	.170	.230
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.111	.145	.135	.189
Aya-23-8B	.135	.176	.151	.215
Bloomz-7B1	.063	.090	.077	.119
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.184	.208	.192	.241
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.170	.194	.175	.227
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.047	.134	.051	.143

Table 35: PTP_{small}^{Italian} evaluated on instruction-tuned models.

Model	EP _{Profanity}	A _{Profanity}	EP _{Toxicity}	A _{Toxicity}
Meta-Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	.259	.268	.227	.266
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	.220	.228	.193	.225
Aya-23-8B	.275	.277	.243	.269
Bloomz-7B1	.172	.177	.163	.177
Occiglot-7B-eu5-Instruct	.293	.287	.262	.277
Salamandra-7B-Instruct	.296	.295	.261	.282
Teuken-7B-Instruct (Ours)	.139	.204	.113	.192

Table 36: PTP_{small}^{Spanish} evaluated on instruction-tuned models.

Hyper-Parameter	SFT	DPO
Epochs	2	1
Weight decay	0.1	0.0
Batch size	128	128
Warmup steps	4300	50
Learning rate	1e-5	3.25e-6
Learning rate schedule	cosine	cosine
Optimizer	AdamW	AdamW
Adam Beta1	0.9	0.9
Adam Beta2	0.95	0.95
Max. Sequence length	2048	1024
Beta (DPO)	NA	0.1

Table 37: Hyperparameter configuration during post-training

Dataset	Sample Size	Min Distance	Languages
IFeval-like [63]	5000	0.0	EN
GSM8K [28]	8000 (EN) / 5000 (DE)	0.0	EN, DE
Winogrande [29]	4000 (per language)	0.0	EN, DE
ARC [41]	180 (per language)	0.0	EN, DE
HellaSwag [45]	2000 (per language)	0.0	EN, DE
Sigma	30000 (per language)	0.1	EN, DE
Sigma Evolved	30000 (per language)	0.2	EN, DE
Sigma Everyday conversations	2260	0.0	EN
OpenMath-instruct 2 [50]	20000 (EN) / 5000 (DE)	0.0	EN, DE
Teuken Guide	20000 (EN) / 5000 (DE)	0.0	EN, DE
Teuken Self Awareness SFT	1130	0.0	EN, DE

Table 38: SFT datasets including sample size, minimum distance, and used languages.

Dataset	Sample Size	Languages
SauerkrautLM-Fermented	3000	DE
dpo-mix-7k	7000 (EN) / 2500 (per other language)	EN,DE,FR,IT
truthy-dpo	1016 (EN) / 500 (per other language)	EN,DE,FR,IT
Winogrande	1500	EN
ARC	180	EN
HellaSwag	750	EN

Table 39: DPO datasets including sample size and languages.

(a) Cross-lingual avg. MT-Bench-X

(b) MT-Bench-EN

(c) MT-Bench-DE

(d) MT-Bench-FR

(e) MT-Bench-IT

(f) MT-Bench-ES

Figure 20: In-depth MT-Bench-X quality assessment by GPT-4.

LAN	Curated (M)	Web (M)	Curated in %	Total (M)	%
bg	21,241	23,827	47.13	60,803	1.13
cs	6,231	46,950	11.72	73,724	1.33
da	6,223	18,269	25.41	33,149	0.61
de	36,865	312,216	10.56	470,396	8.73
el	21,086	40,521	34.23	83,136	1.54
en	212,905	1,453,724	12.77	2,787,190	41.67
es	23,797	296,048	7.44	443,002	8.00
et	8,788	6,258	58.41	19,356	0.38
fi	3,236	36,020	8.24	54,749	0.98
fr	30,617	333,625	8.41	487,932	9.11
ga	474	75	86.26	699	0.01
hr	15,302	1	99.99	18,894	0.38
hu	3,378	37,574	8.25	56,178	1.02
it	19,842	169,183	10.50	246,422	4.73
lt	1,991	9,147	17.87	15,522	0.28
lv	1,981	5,687	25.83	10,754	0.19
mt	3,517	0.5	99.99	4,337	0.09
nl	6,790	125,191	5.14	186,390	3.30
pl	9,400	67,404	12.24	105,835	1.92
pt	6,673	136,378	4.66	202,858	3.58
ro	4,526	26,006	14.82	42,806	0.76
sk	40,130	11,170	78.23	65,600	1.28
sl	12,603	1,229	91.12	17,322	0.35
sv	4,080	40,096	9.24	61,333	1.10
code	301,726	-	100.00	534,170	7.54
Total	803,401	3,196,599	100.00	6,082,559	100.00

Table 40: Comparison of token counts (in millions) between curated and web data across different languages. The total word count reflects the sum of both curated and web-sourced data after deduplication and filtering. Source code is treated separately from natural language data.